

Managing Editor's Column

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Dear J.UCS Community,

In this issue you find eight papers spanning a wide spectrum, from topics to the countries the authors come from! I am sure you will enjoy the papers close to your field.

Have you already tried out the new feature "Links into Future?" To see how it works, go for example to http://www.jucs.org/jucs_3.4/formalizing_database and then click on "Links into Future". Any feedback on this new feature or any comments on any of the papers in this issue are welcome.

Concerning comments, note that there is a button "Write Comment" available for every paper. We hope that the J.UCS community - readers, editors and authors - will make more and more use of this "increased interactivity" possibility.

Finally, since this is the last regular issue in 2007, I'd like to take this opportunity to send you my best wishes for the new year 2008: I hope it will be a good year for you, your families and for J.UCS.

All the best,

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'H. Maurer', with a long horizontal flourish extending to the right.

Hermann Maurer
email: hmaurer@iicm.edu